

Introduction to the analysis of heart rate variability from 5-minute recordings

Paolo Maccallini

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In this document I introduce the analysis of five-minute recordings of R-R intervals, the intervals between two R waves of the heart. I show how to calculate in different ways the variance of this time series, which goes under the name of Heart Rate Variability (HRV); I also show how to apply the discrete Fourier transform to the signal and how to study the resulting harmonics. The biological meanings of these measures are also introduced. To exemplify the theory, I perform a study on about 500 daily recordings of a single subject using the R package RHRV. I also present the results of a small study on ME/CFS patients and matched healthy controls.

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1 Heart Rate Variability

1.1 Heart rate regulation

The parameter that probably better describes the overall activity of the cardiac pump is its cardiac output (CO), which is defined as the product of the volume of blood ejected during the systole (stroke volume, SV) by the number of systoles per minute (heart rate, HR). CO is usually normalized with respect to the surface of the body (body area) and indicated as cardiac index (CI), expressed in $\frac{L}{m^2min}$ (1). In Figure 1 you can see the density of probability of CI in a sample of 50 healthy subjects obtained by pooling measures from two studies (2, 3). Further comments on this pooled sample can be found in (4).

Figure 1. Probability density of Cardiac Index (Cardiac Output normalized with respect to body area) expressed in $\frac{L}{m^2min}$ in a sample of 50 healthy subjects (4).

The link between CO and mean blood pressure (MAP) is given by Poiseuille's law which states that CO is given by MAP divided by systemic vascular resistance (SVR) (5) and MAP is one of the variables that the body uses to monitor the cardiac output. In particular, *baroreceptors* can sense the deformation of the arterial walls, which is proportional to MAP. In other words, the arterial walls act as a transducer that converts a barometric signal into a deformation one. The presence of transducers is a characteristic of many man-made instruments, like the thermocouple that generates an electric potential that is proportional to the temperature of the junction between the two conductors (6). This information travels across the aortic depressor nerve which joins the X cranial nerve pair (also known as vagus nerve), and along the sinus nerve (also known as Hering's nerve) into the IX cranial nerve pair. These afferent signals reach the *nucleus tractus solitarius* (NTS); from there, secondary neurons send glutamatergic projections to inhibitory neurons of caudal ventrolateral medulla (cVLM) which synapse into rostral ventrolateral medulla (rVLM) from which the sympathetic efferent neurons to the heart originate: their signal to the cardiac muscle is responsible for temporary increases in heart rate. From NTS another bundle of glutamatergic neurons synapses to the ambiguous nucleus (AN) in the medulla, and to the dorsal motor nucleus (DMN) of the vagus nerve; from here, the parasympathetic efferent signal reaches the heart: it is responsible for maintaining a stable heart rate, at a lower frequency of the one that the cardiac muscle would have if no signal were present from the autonomic nervous system, which is of about 110 beats per minute. More precisely, when it is required a reduction in MAP, the efferent sympathetic system is inhibited

and the parasympathetic system is activated; when an increase of MAP is required, there is no inhibition of the sympathetic system and no activation of the parasympathetic system.

Figure 2. Short-term cardiovascular control model, from Fig. 2 of (7) and Fig. 4.12 of (8), with modifications.

It should be mentioned that the sympathetic efferent signal is also responsible for modulating SVR and venous capacitance: when it is not inhibited there is an increase in SVR and a decrease in venous capacitance; when it is inhibited, the effect is the opposite (8). Baroreceptor-mediated cardiovascular control involves also cortical and subcortical regions (insular cortex, anterior cingulate cortex, amygdala, and cerebellum) via their connections with Medulla Oblongata (9). Renin secretion by kidneys is regulated via sympathetic signaling and the renin-angiotensin system has several effects on the homeostasis of volume and osmolarity of organic fluids (8) and is also known to effect cardiac function (7).

The sympathetic and the parasympathetic branches of the ANS, and the renin-angiotensin system affect the heart rate simultaneously and with a different reaction velocity so that the activity of each of these three systems affects the harmonics of the RR series (Eq. 1) with specific frequencies. This was demonstrated in a pivotal work published in 1981 (7) that is worth illustrating here with some detail. The experiment was performed on dogs whose ECG was recorded during the administration of different drugs. After blockage of parasympathetic muscarinic transmission by administration of glycopyrrolate, the mid (0.12 Hz) and high-frequency peak (0.25 Hz) of the periodograms of RR (par. 1.4) were abolished, while the low-frequency peak (0.04 Hz) is reduced in amplitude. On the other hand, with the use of propranol, a β -adrenergic receptor antagonist, only the low-frequency peak was reduced. If the two drugs were administered simultaneously, the fluctuations in HR tended to disappear, making the heart pump in a regular, metronome-like fashion. The authors were then able to draw some important conclusions and I report here a passage from the original paper:

“Therefore, our data indicate that the parasympathetic nervous system mediates heart rate fluctuations at frequencies corresponding to the mid- and high-frequency peaks of the power spectrum, whereas both the sympathetic and parasympathetic systems may mediate the low-frequency fluctuations.

They then administered nonapeptide converting enzyme inhibitor to block the renin-angiotensin system and they observed a 2 to 4-fold increase in the low-frequency powerband, suggesting that the renin-angiotensin system normally damps down the harmonics of RR in the lower spectrum of frequency.

The discovery of variability in HR (heart rate variability, HRV) is not a recent one. At the end of the 16th century, Galileo Galilei used his heart as a chronometer in his experiments of mechanics, implicitly assuming that the frequency of the cardiac muscle is stable in time. But in 1733 Stephen Hales published a manuscript in which he observed that the distance between two consecutive heartbeats varies during the respiratory cycle (10): in fact, the HR increases during inspiration and decreases during expiration and this cycle goes under the name of respiratory sinus arrhythmia (RSA). Other processes that are associated with changes in HR are the baroreceptor reflex (associated with the 0.12 Hz peak) and peripheral vasomotor tone (0.04 Hz peak) (11) (Table 1).

Frequency Peak (Hz)	Regulatory System	Associated Process
0.04	PNS, SNS, RAS	peripheral vasomotor tone
0.12	PNS	baroreceptor reflex
0.25	PNS	breathing

Table 1. Peaks of the periodogram of the RR series, cardiac regulatory systems that cause them, and biological cycles they are associated with.

1.2 RR interval and heart rate

We define RR interval as the time interval between two R waves, as registered by the electrocardiogram (ECG) or by other, simpler, devices. In ECG, the R wave is the projection on lead II of the ventricular depolarization vector (VDV) which indicates the start of ventricular isovolumic contraction (start of systole) and the closure of the atrioventricular valves (the first sound that can be heard with the stethoscopes) (5). Mathematically:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad RR_i = (Time_i - Time_{(i-1)})10^3$$

where RR_i is expressed in milliseconds while $Time_i$ is expressed in seconds. Therefore, heart rate (HR) is defined as follows

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad HR_i = \frac{60}{(Time_i - Time_{(i-1)})} = \frac{60 \cdot 10^3}{RR_i}$$

and it is expressed in beats per minute. Note that while ECG recordings are the gold standard for RR series acquisition, measurements from sensors mounted on moistened chest belts have proven to be reliable and accurate by several studies, as reviewed in (12).

1.3 Time domain analysis

The mean and the standard deviation of the RR intervals are given respectively by

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \overline{RR} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N RR_i$$

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad SDNN = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\overline{RR} - RR_i)^2}{N-1}}$$

Note that $SDNN$ is affected by the length of the recording, therefore it can be used only for comparison between recordings of the same length. In 5-minute recordings, normal values of $SDNN$ are included in 32-93 ms with a mean value of 50 and a standard deviation of 16 (13). If we make the position

$$\Delta RR_i = RR_{(i+1)} - RR_{(i)} = (Time_{(i+1)} + Time_{(i-1)} - 2Time_i)10^3$$

we then indicate $NN50$ the number of intervals such that $\Delta RR_i > 50ms$. We then define the index:

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad pNN50 = \frac{NN50}{N-1} 100$$

Figure 3. Triangle with the same area of the histogram of an RR recording (9th of July, 2022).

The mean and the standard deviation of ΔRR_i are given respectively by

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad \overline{\Delta RR} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta RR_i$$

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad SDSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\Delta\overline{RR} - \Delta RR_i)^2}{N-1}}$$

We also consider the quadratic mean of ΔRR_i :

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad rMSSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \Delta RR_i^2}{N-1}}$$

In 5-minute recordings, normal values of $rMSSD$ are included in 19-75 ms with a mean value of 42 and a standard deviation of 15 (13). If we indicate $Q_1(\Delta RR)$, $Q_3(\Delta RR)$ the first and third interquartile of the distribution of ΔRR , the quantity

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad IRRR = Q_3(\Delta RR) - Q_1(\Delta RR)$$

is considered an overall measure of HRV. If we assume that $RR \sim N(\overline{RR}, SDNN^2)$ and assuming that $RR_{(i+1)}$ and RR_i are independent, we can say that $\Delta RR \sim N(0, 2SDNN^2)$ which leads to the relationships $\Delta\overline{RR} \approx 0, SDSD \approx \sqrt{2} \cdot SDNN$. Moreover, we have

$$\begin{aligned} IRRR = Q_3(\Delta RR) - Q_1(\Delta RR) &= \sqrt{2} \cdot SDNN \cdot \phi_{0.75} + \Delta\overline{RR} - \sqrt{2} \cdot SDNN \cdot \phi_{0.25} - \Delta\overline{RR} = \\ &= \sqrt{2} \cdot SDNN (\phi_{0.75} - \phi_{0.25}) \approx 2\sqrt{2} \cdot SDNN \cdot 0.67 = 1.9 \cdot SDNN \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4. Histograms for SDNN, HRV index, rMSSD and other time-domain parameters for about 500 recordings of five minutes each. The mean value of each distribution is also indicated (red lines).

The width of the bins is 7.825 ms. The base of the triangle is named $TINN$ (Eq. 11). The height of the triangle is given by the maximum value reached by the bars. In other words, $IRRR$ is a measure of the standard deviation of RR . Another measure of variability is

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad MADRR = Q_2(|\Delta RR|)$$

where Q_2 is the second interquartile (the median). If we now consider the histogram of RR intervals with a bino of 7.8125 ms and the triangle with the same area of $bin \cdot N$ and with the height given by the maximum value of the histogram itself, indicated Max_{histo} (Figure 3), if we name $TINN$ the base of the triangle, we have

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad TINN = 2 \frac{bin \cdot N}{Max_{histo}}$$

This is another way to measure HRV since $TINN$ is proportional to the variance of RR . Note that in the above definition, $2bin$ is a constant that does not depend on the measures we are analyzing. This suggests to consider the following definition:

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad HRV_{index} = \frac{TINN}{2 \cdot bin} = \frac{N}{Max_{histo}}$$

Some of these measures have overlapping biological meanings, as summarized in Table 2. One common choice is to consider $SDNN$, HRV_{index} as a measure of overall HRV and $rMSSD$ for high frequency HRV. This applies to recordings of five minutes, while for longer recordings other indexes can be added. The histograms of $SDNN$, HRV_{index} , $rMSSD$ calculated for four hundred 5-minute recordings (single subject, different days) are reported in Figure 4.

Figure 5. Periodograms for four of the available 5-minute recordings. Only the LF and HF range were included since the ULF and VLF are not reliable for short recordings. No smoothing was applied.

measure of overall HRV	$SDNN, IRRR, TINN, HRV_{index}$
high frequency components of HRV	$pNN50, SDSD, rMSSD, MADDR$

Table 2. Filed of application of the different indexes of time-dependent analysis for recordings of five minutes (11, 13).

Measure	Mean (SD)	Interval
RR (ms)	926 (90)	785-1160
SDNN (ms)	50 (16)	32-93
rMSSD (ms)	42 (15)	19-75

Table 3. Intervals in healthy subjects for 5-minute recordings for time domain parameters (13).

1.4 Frequency domain analysis

The primary method for frequency analysis of HRV is the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), introduced in par. 3.2. The discrete signal in this case is the series RR_i , and according to Eq. 33 its DFT can be written

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad X(k) = \sum_{q=1}^m RR_q e^{-2\pi i(q-1)\frac{k-1}{m}}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Remember that the use of DFT has as a prerequisite the even sampling of the signal, therefore it is necessary to interpolate the RR series to obtain a proper input for the DFT. Otherwise, if no interpolation is performed, it is necessary to use other frequency analysis functions, like the Lomb-Scargle method. Whatever the method of choice, the results of the analysis can be visualized as a periodogram, the plot of the power of the signal as a function of its frequency (see par. 3.3), smoothed with various methods.

Band	Range (Hz)	Power (ms^2)	
		Mean (SD)	Interval
Ultra Low Frequency (ULF)	[0, 0.003]	-	-
Very Low Frequency (VLF)	[0.003, 0.04]	-	-
Low Frequency (LF)	[0.04, 0.15]	519 (291)	193-1009
High Frequency (HF)	[0.15, 0.4]	657 (777)	83-3630
LF/HF	-	2.8 (2.6)	1.1-11.6

Table 4. Frequency ranges of common use in spectral analysis of HRV signals (14). Intervals in healthy subjects for 5-minute recordings for the powers in LF and HF (13).

Usually, the DFT (or other equivalent method) is not applied to the whole recording. The reason is that there is likely an evolution of the signal, with a change of the power for each band: we

say that the signal is, in general, not stationary. In this case, we apply the DFT to windows within the whole recording, with a fixed length in time (*size*), and shifted with respect to the other of a period of time shorter than the *size* (*shift*) to have a partial overlapping between consecutive windows. This particular use of the DFT is called Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT). For each band, an average can be then calculated over all the windows. How long should be the *size*? It depends on the bands one is interested in: the European and American Task Force on Standards in HRV (14) recommends the choice of a window that includes at least 10 complete periods of the component with the lowest frequency. Therefore, if we want to include the LF band, we need a window with a size of at least $\frac{10}{0.04} = 250$ s which is 4 minutes and 10 seconds. This means that in a recording of five minute there might be no necessity of smaller time windows. Accordingly, it has been documented that in 5-minute recordings, windows of 1, 2, and 3 minutes produces results for LF and total power that poorly correlate with the results generated by a window of 4 minutes (12). The histograms of *LF*, *HF*, *LF/HF* calculated for four hundred 5-minute recordings (single subject, different days) each are reported in Figure 6. Some authors also use normalized versions of *LF*, *HF* defined as follows

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad LF_{nu} = \frac{LF}{LF+HF}, \quad HF_{nu} = \frac{HF}{LF+HF}$$

These are dimensionless quantities and their main peculiarity is to reduce the within-subject and across-subject variability and can be useful for the comparison of the results from different laboratories and research groups (15). The histograms of the normalized power bands for 500 recordings are reported in Figure 7. Reference values for 5-minute recordings are in Table 4.

Figure 6. Histograms for LF, HF, LF/HF for about 500 recordings of five minutes each. The mean value of each distribution is also indicated (red lines).

	PI-ME/CFS	HC	<i>p</i> value
females/males	8/5	10/9	0.725
age	40.769(15.498)	41(13.569)	1
BMI	26.585(5.214)	25.868(3.58)	0.788

Table 5. Comparison between demographics of 13 PI-ME/CFS and 19 healthy subjects. I used the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test for age and body mass index (BMI), while the Fisher-Irvin test was employed for the sex comparison.

1.5 Experimental data

In this document, I used data from two experiments. The first experiment consists of a set of more than 500 recordings of five minutes measured from July 2022 to February 2024, on a single subject. Measures were recorded in the morning, in a supine position, after 5 minutes of rest in the same position. The RR series was recorded by a Polar H9 sensor mounted on a moistened chest belt. The HR monitor was connected via Bluetooth to a smartphone and data was uploaded to a server via Elite HRV and downloaded to my PC in text format.

Figure 7. Histograms for LFnu and HFnu for about 500 recordings of five minutes each. The mean value of each distribution is also indicated (red lines).

	PI-ME/CFS	HC	<i>p</i> value	correction
HR (beats/minute)	74.224(11.805)	70.962(6.84)	0.108	0.472
RR (<i>ms</i>)	830.813(155.74)	852.319(75.169)	0.108	0.472
SDNN (<i>ms</i>)	123.358(27.35)	133.131(32.813)	0.472	0.472
rMSSD (<i>ms</i>)	29.522(8.79)	40.486(13.668)	0.022	0.198
pNN50	6.024(5.639)	13.584(9.194)	0.013	0.13
LF (<i>ms</i> ²)	808.709(503.236)	1270.223(1085.232)	0.377	0.472
LFnu	0.762(0.131)	0.688(0.188)	0.27	0.472
HF (<i>ms</i> ²)	232.073(218.463)	693.531(892.05)	0.033	0.264
HFnu	0.238(0.131)	0.312(0.188)	0.27	0.472
LF/HF	4.982(4.017)	2.979(1.659)	0.27	0.472
Total Power (<i>ms</i> ²)	1040.783(607.734)	1963.755(1865.278)	0.092	0.472

Table 6. Results for time domain and frequency domain HRV data. The Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test was used for *p* values calculation, and the Benjamini-Hochberg correction was then applied.

The second dataset comes from an exploratory research launched in 2016 by the Division of Intramural Research of the National Institute of Health (NIH). The study performed deep phenotyping on a cohort of well-characterized post-infectious ME/CFS patients (PI-ME/CFS) (16). In particular, 24-hour HRV recordings were collected on 13 patients and 19 healthy controls (Table 5). For time-dependent analysis I compared the two groups for the values of HR, SDNN, rMSSD, and pNN50, averaged on the entire recording; for frequency domain analysis I used only the measures of LF and HF from the interval included between the 5th minute and the 10th (Table 6, Figure 8, Figure 9). Data were accessed via mapMECFS (17). This statistical analysis is performed by the script in paragraph 4.4.

Figure 8. Comparison between 13 PI-ME/CFS (cfs) patients and 19 healthy controls (hc) for time-domain HRV measures. The first quartile, median, and third quartile are indicated for each measure. The mean value is indicated by a triangle. P values are from the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test and are not corrected for multiple comparisons (see Table 6 for the corrected p values). All the measures are averaged over 24 hours.

RR	SDNN	rMSSD	pNN50	LF	LFnu	HF	HFnu	LF/HF	cfs/hc	pos.	dur.	
-	-	-	-	=	-	=	-	-	17/17	supine	5'	(18)
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	=	↓	↓	↑	45/25	supine	5'	(19)
=	=	=	=	=	-	=	=	=	32/19	supine	5'	(20)
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	↓	↓	↑	45/25	supine	5'	(20)
-	-	-	-	↓	-	↓	-	-	34/32	sitting	5'	(21)
=	=	↓	↓	=	=	↓	=	=	13/19	-	24h/5'	(16)

Table 7. Comparison between the results of a few studies that measured HRV parameters in ME/CFS patients vs healthy controls. For reference (20), the first row is relative to males only, and the second row to females only. For reference (16), results of time domain analysis are averaged on recordings of 24 hours, while frequency domain measures are relative to five-minute recordings. pos: position; dur: duration.

1.6 HRV in ME/CFS

I searched for studies that measured HRV in ME/CFS and compared the results with healthy controls. I focused on papers published in the last five years, with the subject at rest and measures on windows of five minutes. I collected the results in Table 7 and the conclusion is that the most consistent finding is a reduction of power in the HF band which points to a blunted parasympathetic regulatory input to the heart.

Figure 9. Comparison between 13 PI-ME/CFS (cfs) patients and 19 healthy controls (hc) for frequency domain HRV measures. Only the measures relative to the interval between minute 5 and minute 10 of the recording were considered. P values are not corrected (see Table 6 for the corrected p values).

2 Use of R package RHRV

2.1 Loading the data

To install the package and to use it in your script, write

```
install.packages("RHRV")
library(RHRV)
```

To load HRV data we first need to create a list object that will contain it. We use the following instructions:

```
install.packages("RHRV")
library(RHRV)
```

We can now load the measures. In this case, readings come from a Polar H9 sensor, they were transferred via Bluetooth to a smartphone (Android) with the application Elite HRV installed. The raw RR interval data (milliseconds) were then downloaded as txt file, one for each five-minute recording (one recording per day). The name of each recording is of the type YYYY-MM-DD-HH-MM-SS.txt, where YYYY stands for the year, MM for the month, and so forth. To initiate the list that will contain the reading and the results of the analyses we are going to do on them, we write:

```
hrv.data<-CreateHRVData()
hrv.data<-SetVerbose(hrv.data,T)
```

Now we need to extract the date of the recording from its name and convert it into the format used by RHRV:

```
date.str<-gsub(".txt","",file_name)] # remove ".txt" from file name
date.str<-strptime(date.str,format="%Y-%m-%d %H-%M-%S")
date.str<-format(date.str,format="%d/%m/%Y %H:%M:%S")
```

where `file_name` is of the type YYYY-MM-DD-HH-MM-SS.txt. Now, we perform the actual storage of the RR intervals:

```
hrv.data<-LoadBeatAscii(hrv.data,file_names,RecordPath=folder_path,scale=0.001,datetime=date.str)
```

Note that the scale is 0.001 because our readings are in milliseconds. Note also that `folder_path` contains the path to the reading. If we have more than one reading, as it is usually the case, we can load them using a loop:

```
days<-length(file_names)
hrv.data<-list()
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateHRVData()
  hrv.data[[i]]<-SetVerbose(hrv.data[[i]],T)
  date.str<-gsub(".txt","",file_names[[i]]) # remove ".txt" from file name
  date.str<-strptime(date.str,format="%Y-%m-%d %H-%M-%S")
  date.str<-format(date.str,format="%d/%m/%Y %H:%M:%S")
  hrv.data[[i]]<-LoadBeatAscii(hrv.data[[i]],file_names[[i]],
    RecordPath=folder_path,scale=0.001,datetime=date.str)
```

```
}
```

2.2 Instantaneous heart rate and its interpolation

Instantaneous heart rate can be calculated from RR intervals using Eq. 2, after removal of anomalous beats. A type of anomaly that we don't want to interfere with HR calculation is represented by ectopic beats, those contractions of the cardiac muscle that are not due to autonomic control but rather to automatism of the cardiac fibers. Other anomalies can be due to errors in the sensor and noise. The filtering process is carried out by eliminating the intervals that are too different from the previous and the following ones; moreover, RR intervals that are below or above a threshold deduced from our knowledge of the distribution of RR intervals in humans are removed. Pruning of the raw time series of intervals and calculation of the instantaneous HR is performed by the following instructions:

```
for (i in 1:days) {  
  hrv.data[[i]]<-BuildNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])  
  hrv.data[[i]]<-FilterNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])  
}
```

Non-interpolated instantaneous heart rate

Figure 10. Noninterpolated instantaneous HR for one of the readings (9th of July, 2022).

This gives the noninterpolated instantaneous HR and we can plot it for one of the recordings (Figure 10):

```
PlotNIHR(hrv.data[[1]])
```

For the subsequent analyses, we need to interpolate the instantaneous HR to have a sampling frequency that is constant (default value: 4 Hz) and without holes due to the filtering process or other causes. To do so we write:

```
for (i in 1:days) {  
  hrv.data[[i]]<-BuildNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])  
  hrv.data[[i]]<-FilterNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])  
}
```

```
}
```

2.3 Time domain analysis

A complete time-dependent analysis of our recordings is performed with the following instructions:

```
for (i in 1:days) {  
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateTimeAnalysis(hrv.data[[i]])  
}
```

This will derive, for all the recordings, the calculation of the indexes illustrated in par. 1.3. So, for instance, to access the SDNN of the first recording, we write:

```
hrv.data[[1]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$SDNN
```

If we want on the screen all the results for the first recording we write:

```
hrv.data[[1]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]
```

Note that some results are calculated only for recordings longer than five minutes (like SDANN, not discussed in this document). The histograms of $SDNN$, HRV_{index} , $rMSSD$ over four hundred recordings of five minutes each are reported in Figure 3. The plot is generated by the following instructions:

```
SDNN.vec<-c()  
HRVi.vec<-c()  
rMSSD.vec<-c()  
for (i in 1:days) {  
  SDNN.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$SDNN  
  HRVi.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$HRVi  
  rMSSD.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$rMSSD  
}  
dev.new()  
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,3,2,3),2,2)  
layout(mat=layout.mat)  
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))  
#  
vector<-seq(from=(min(SDNN.vec)-2*delta.bin),to=(max(SDNN.vec)+2*delta.bin),by=delta.bin)  
hist(SDNN.vec,vector,xlab="SDNN (ms)",ylab="SDNN count",main="")  
abline(v=mean(SDNN.vec),col="red",lwd=2)  
#  
vector<-seq(from=(min(HRVi.vec)-2*2),to=(max(HRVi.vec)+2*2),by=2)  
hist(HRVi.vec,vector,xlab="HRVi",ylab="HRVi count",main="")  
abline(v=mean(HRVi.vec),col="red",lwd=2)  
#  
vector<-seq(from=(min(rMSSD.vec)-2*delta.bin),to=(max(rMSSD.vec)+2*delta.bin),by=delta.bin)  
hist(rMSSD.vec,vector,xlab="rMSSD (ms)",ylab="rMSSD count",main="")  
abline(v=mean(rMSSD.vec),col="red",lwd=2)
```

2.4 Frequency domain analysis

To perform a complete frequency analysis we first need to create the object that will store it:

```
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateFreqAnalysis(hrv.data[[i]])
}
```

To store the periodogram in the list, we add the following instructions inside the loop:

```
hrv.data[[i]]<-CalculatePSD(hrv.data[[i]],method="pgram",doPlot=F)
```

The method selected is based on the DFT, but other methods are available. We also ask to avoid plotting the periodogram, since we have several hundreds of recordings. If we now open the `hrv.data` list, we find that each recording has a `FreqAnalysis` object and that this object has a `periodogram` section where we find a vector of the frequencies for which the power has been calculated (`freq`), a vector with the powers estimated (`spec`), and string that specifies the method (`method`). To plot the periodograms in Figure 5 we used the following instructions:

```
dev.new()
par(mfrow=c(2,2))
for (i in 1:4) {
  PlotPSD(hrv.data[[i]],ULFmin=NULL,ULFmax=NULL,VLFmin=NULL,VLFmax=NULL, ,LFmin=0.04,
    ylim=c(1e-01,1e+6),main=hrv.data[[i]]$datetime, log="")
}
```

Note how I excluded the ULF range and the VLF range, which are not reliable for recordings of five minutes. I also specified `LFmin` because the default value is 0.05, for some reason. Note also setting `log=""` which is necessary to avoid a logarithmic scale on the y-axis which would flatten the periodogram and make the picks not visible. The calculation of the power bands requires the specification of the size of the windows used for the DFT and their shift. In a five-minute recording, there is no necessity for smaller time windows, therefore we set a size of 300 s and an arbitrary shift. To perform the analysis for each one of the readings we must insert in the loop the following instruction:

```
hrv.data[[i]]<-CalculatePowerBand(hrv.data[[i]],LFmin=0.04,size=120,shift=30)
```

To plot the histograms of the power bands (Figure 6) we can use the following instructions:

```
LF.vec<-c()
HF.vec<-c()
LFHF.vec<-c()
for (i in 1:days) {
  LF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LF
  HF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$HF
  LFHF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LFHF
}
dev.new()
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,3,2,3),2,2)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
minimo<-min(LF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LF.vec,vector,xlab=expression(paste("LF (",ms^{2},")")),ylab="count",main="")
```

```

abline(v=mean(LF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
minimo<-min(HF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(HF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(HF.vec,vector,xlab=expression(paste("HF (",ms^{2},")")),ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(HF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
minimo<-min(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LFHF.vec,vector,xlab="LF/HF",ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)

```

It may be of interest to derive the normalized values of the power bands (Eq. 14). Since these values are not computed, to my knowledge, by RHRV, we derive them with the following loop:

```

LFnuHFnu<-data.frame(date=c(rep(NA,days)),LFnu=c(rep(1,days)),HFnu=c(rep(1,days)))
for (i in 1:days) {
  LFnuHFnu$date[i]<-as.character(hrv.data[[i]]$datetime)
  LF<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LF
  HF<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$HF
  LFnuHFnu$LFnu[i]<-LF/(LF+HF)
  LFnuHFnu$HFnu[i]<-HF/(LF+HF)
}

```

We can then use lines similar to those that generate the histograms of the power bands, to generate Figure 7. The complete script used in this chapter can be found in par. 4.5.

3 Mathematical notes

3.1 Discrete Fourier analysis

Let us consider a signal $x(t)$ defined in $]0, T[$ and let us extend its definition on \mathbb{R} by assuming that $x(t + T) = x(t)$. Then we define the Fourier series of x the following trigonometric polynomial:

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \wp_n(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) \right)$$

with

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \begin{cases} a_k = \frac{2}{P} \int_{-L}^L x(t) \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{P}t\right) dt, & k = 0, 1, \dots \\ b_k = \frac{2}{P} \int_{-L}^L x(t) \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{P}t\right) dt, & k = 1, 2, \dots \end{cases}$$

It can be shown that $P_n(t)$ if $x \in C^1(]0, T[)$ and $x \in C^0(\mathbb{R})$, then $P_n(t)$ totally converges to $f(t)$ over \mathbb{R} (22). When instead of having a continue function, we have discrete data, we face the following problem: given a series of couples t_i, x_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ we are interested in finding the $2n + 1$ coefficients that solve the linear system

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad x_i = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) \right), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

Remember: m is the number of measures available while n defines the number of coefficients. The methods involved in the discussion of this problem go under the name of Discrete Fourier Analysis (DFA) which is based on the application of the least square method (LSQ) (23). In particular, we consider the residuals

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad R_i = x_i - \frac{a_0}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{P}t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{P}t_i\right) \right), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

and we search the values of the coefficients that minimize the sum of squares $SSR = \sum_{i=1}^m R_i^2$. We must find where the gradient of SSR is zero, as a first step:

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial a_k} = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\partial R_i^2}{\partial a_k} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial a_k} = \begin{cases} -\sum_{i=1}^m R_i = 0, & k = 0 \\ -2 \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) = 0, & k = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial b_k} = \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\partial R_i^2}{\partial b_k} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \frac{\partial R_i}{\partial b_k} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Therefore, we have $2n + 1$ equations in $2n + 1$ unknowns (the coefficients):

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m R_i = 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) = 0, & k = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ \sum_{i=1}^m R_i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_i\right) = 0, & k = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases}$$

The first equation can be written more conveniently as follows:

$$\frac{ma_0}{2} + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i$$

For the other equations, we write

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

⋮

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

⋮

$$\frac{a_0}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) + \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right)$$

To simplify the notation we introduce the following notation:

$$\begin{aligned} v_k &= \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n & c_{k,h} &= \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad k, h = 0, 1, \dots, n \\ u_k &= \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n & z_{h,k} &= \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad \begin{matrix} h = 0, 1, \dots, n \\ k = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{matrix} \\ s_{k,h} &= \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad k, h = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

Note that while $c_{k,h} = c_{h,k}$ and $s_{k,h} = s_{h,k}$, it is not true in general that $z_{h,k} = z_{k,h}$. We also introduce the following vectors:

$$V = [v_0 \quad v_1 \quad \dots \quad v_m \quad u_0 \quad u_1 \quad \dots \quad u_m]^T, \quad \alpha = \left[\frac{a_0}{2} \quad a_1 \quad \dots \quad a_m \quad b_0 \quad b_1 \quad \dots \quad b_m \right]^T$$

All that said, the system in Eq. 21 can now then be written

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad \begin{bmatrix} c_{0,0} & c_{0,1} & \dots & c_{0,n} & z_{0,1} & z_{0,2} & \dots & z_{0,n} \\ c_{1,0} & c_{1,1} & \dots & c_{1,n} & z_{1,1} & z_{1,2} & \dots & z_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ c_{n,0} & c_{n,1} & \dots & c_{n,n} & z_{n,1} & z_{n,2} & \dots & z_{n,n} \\ z_{0,1} & z_{1,1} & \dots & z_{n,1} & s_{1,1} & s_{1,2} & \dots & s_{1,n} \\ z_{0,2} & z_{1,2} & \dots & z_{n,2} & s_{2,1} & s_{2,2} & \dots & s_{2,n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ z_{0,n} & z_{1,n} & \dots & z_{n,n} & s_{n,1} & s_{n,2} & \dots & s_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0/2 \\ a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_0 \\ v_1 \\ \vdots \\ v_n \\ u_1 \\ u_2 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow H\alpha = V$$

If we introduce the $m \times (2n + 1)$ matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \dots & \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \dots & \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_1\right) \\ 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \dots & \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \dots & \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_2\right) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_m\right) & \dots & \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_m\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_m\right) & \dots & \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T}t_m\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

we have $A^T A = H$. As a partial proof, let us consider the case $m = 4$ and $n = 1$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & A^T A \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_3\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_4\right) \\ \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_3\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_4\right) \\ \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_3\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_4\right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_1\right) \\ 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_2\right) \\ 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_3\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_3\right) \\ 1 & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_4\right) & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_4\right) \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 4 & \sum_{i=1}^4 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) & \sum_{i=1}^4 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) \\ \sum_{i=1}^4 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) & \sum_{i=1}^4 \cos^2\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) & \sum_{i=1}^4 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) \\ \sum_{i=1}^4 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) & \sum_{i=1}^4 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) & \sum_{i=1}^4 \sin^2\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t_i\right) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{0,0} & c_{0,1} & z_{0,1} \\ c_{1,0} & c_{1,1} & z_{1,1} \\ z_{1,0} & z_{1,1} & s_{1,1} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= H \end{aligned}$$

We assume that the m nodes are equally spaced in $[0, 2L]$, therefore:

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad t_i = T \frac{i-1}{m-1}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

With the help of a drawing (Figure 11) it is easy to verify the following result:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}\right) = \sin\left(2\pi \frac{k}{m-1}\right) + \sin\left(2\pi \frac{2k}{m-1}\right) + \dots + \sin\left(2\pi \frac{m-2}{m-1}k\right) = 0$$

Therefore, if x_i is defined by Eq. 23, we have

$$\begin{aligned} z_{h,k} &= \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2(k+h)\pi}{T} t_i\right) - \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) = 0 - \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 11. For each angle $2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}$ with $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ a segment from $(\cos(2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}), 0)$ to $(\sin(2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}), 0)$ is plotted. Its color is blue if $\sin(2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}) > 0$, red otherwise. We used the values $m = 20, k = 5$ to generate this plotting with the script in par. 4.1. This figure shows that $\sum_{i=1}^m \sin(2k\pi \frac{i-1}{m-1}) = 0$.

This relation must be true for any possible values of k, h . Therefore, in particular, it must be true for $k = h$, which implies that $z_{h,k} = 0$. It is also possible to show that the following relationships are true if Eq. 23 holds:

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad c_{k,h} = \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq h \\ m, & k = h = 0 \\ \frac{m}{2}, & k = h \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad s_{k,h} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq h \\ \frac{m}{2}, & k = h \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

This means that H is a diagonal matrix, and more precisely that

$$H = \text{diag} \left(m, \frac{m}{2}, \frac{m}{2}, \dots, \frac{m}{2} \right)$$

Therefore it is regular (its determinant is $\frac{m^{2n+1}}{2^{2n}}$) and the coefficients for which the gradient of SSR is zero are given by the unique solution of Eq. 22, i.e. $\alpha = H^{-1}V$ or, in other words by

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_0/2 \\ a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_n \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \vdots \\ b_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m^{-1} & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{2}{m} & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{2}{m} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \\ \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \\ \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t_i\right) \\ \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{T} t_i\right) \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2n\pi}{T} t_i\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

The coefficients can be expressed in a more compact way as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad \begin{cases} a_k = \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), & k = 0, 1, \dots, n \\ b_h = \frac{2}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), & h = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases}$$

To verify that these values of the coefficients correspond to the maximum of SSR we must now consider the hessian associated with SSR . By derivation of Eq. 19, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial a_h \partial a_k} &= \begin{cases} \frac{m}{2}, & k = h = 0 \\ 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), & k, h \neq 0 \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial b_h \partial a_k} &= \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), & k = 0 \\ 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), & k \neq 0 \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial b_h \partial b_k} &= 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right), \quad h, k = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial a_h \partial b_k} &= \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), & h = 0 \\ 2 \sum_{i=1}^m \cos\left(\frac{2h\pi}{T} t_i\right) \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t_i\right), & h \neq 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Given Eq. 24 and Eq. 25 we can deduce that

$$\frac{\partial SSR}{\partial a_k \partial a_h} = \begin{cases} \frac{m}{2}, & k = h = 0 \\ 0, & k \neq h \\ m, & k = h \neq 0 \end{cases} \quad \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial a_k \partial b_h} = \frac{\partial SSR}{\partial b_h \partial a_k} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial SSR}{\partial b_k \partial b_h} = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq h \\ m, & k = h \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

We have found that the hessian of SSR is the diagonal matrix $diag\left(\frac{m}{2}, m, m, \dots, m\right)$, therefore SSR has a minimum in the point identified by Eq. 26. All that said, the interpolation of the signal is given by

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad x(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_k \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) + b_k \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) \right), \quad t \in \mathbb{R}$$

3.2 Discrete Fourier Transform

We define Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) of the series of points t_p, x_p with $p = 1, 2, \dots, m$ the vector whose elements are given by

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad X(k) = \sum_{q=1}^m x_q \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_q\right) - i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_q\right) \right) = \sum_{q=1}^m x_q e^{-i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_q}$$

with $k = -n, n-1, \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots, n-1, n$ and assuming $n+1 = m$. Note that i is the imaginary unit number (this is why we now use q as index). We observe that

$$X(k) + X(-k) = 2 \sum_{q=1}^m x_p \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_q\right) = ma_k$$

$$X(k) - X(-k) = -2i \sum_{q=1}^m x_p \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t_q\right) = -imb_k$$

Therefore we can calculate the coefficients in Eq. 26 by calculating the DFT and then considering that $a_k = \frac{X(k) + \bar{X}(k)}{m}$ and $b_k = i \frac{X(k) - \bar{X}(k)}{m}$, where $\bar{X}(k)$ is the conjugate of $X(k)$, which equals $X(-k)$, as it is easy to show. A convenient algorithm for the calculation of the DFT is the Fast Fourier Transform, described in (23). Note that Eq. 27 can be directly expressed in terms of DFT:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= \frac{a_0}{2} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(X(k) \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) + \bar{X}(k) \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) + iX(k) \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) - i\bar{X}(k) \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) \right) = \\ &= \frac{a_0}{2} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(X(k) \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) + i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) \right) + \bar{X}(k) \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) - i \sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{T}t\right) \right) \right) = \\ &= \frac{a_0}{2} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n \left(X(k) e^{i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t} + \bar{X}(k) e^{-i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t} \right) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n X(k) e^{i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^n X(-k) e^{-i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t} \end{aligned}$$

But we note that $\sum_{k=1}^n X(-k) e^{-i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t} = \sum_{k=-n}^{-1} X(k) e^{i\frac{2k\pi}{T}t}$ and also that

$$X(0) + X(-0) = 2X(0) = 2 \sum_{p=1}^m x_p = ma_0 \Rightarrow \frac{X(0)}{m} = \frac{a_0}{2}$$

Therefore, we find

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=0}^n X(k) e^{i \frac{2k\pi}{T} t} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=-n}^{-1} X(k) e^{i \frac{2k\pi}{T} t} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad x(t) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=-n}^n X(k) e^{i \frac{2k\pi}{T} t}$$

The function

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \frac{1}{m} X(k) e^{i \frac{2k\pi}{T} t} = \frac{X(k)}{m} \left(\cos \left(\frac{2k\pi}{P} t \right) + i \sin \left(\frac{2k\pi}{T} t \right) \right)$$

is the k^{th} harmonic component of the original signal and its frequency is given by $f_k = \frac{k}{T}$ which is always a multiple of the *fundamental frequency* $\frac{1}{T}$ of the signal, while its *peak amplitude* is $\frac{X(k)}{m}$. If we introduce the module M_k of $X(k)$ and its phase φ_k we can write $X(k) = M_k e^{-i\varphi_k}$ and therefore the signal $x(t)$ of Eq. 29 can be written

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= \sum_{k=-n}^n \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i\varphi_k} e^{i2\pi f_k t} = \sum_{k=-n}^n \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)} \\ &= \frac{M_0}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_0 + 2\pi f_0 t)} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)} + \sum_{k=-1}^{-n} \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)} \end{aligned}$$

We note now that since $X(0) = \sum_{q=1}^m x_q$, then we have $M_0 = X(0)$ and $\varphi_0 = f_0 = 0$. Moreover, from the observation that $X(-k)$ is the conjugate of $X(k)$ it follows that $M_k = M_{-k}$ and that $\varphi_k = -\varphi_{-k}$, $f_k = -f_{-k}$. Therefore we have

$$\sum_{k=-1}^{-n} \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} e^{-i(\varphi_{-k} + 2\pi f_{-k} t)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} e^{i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)}$$

And the expression of $x(t)$ becomes

$$x(t) = \frac{M_0}{m} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} (e^{-i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)} + e^{i(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)}) = \frac{M_0}{m} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} \cos(\varphi_k + 2\pi f_k t)$$

By applying Euler's formula we conclude that the signal is a sum of cosines:

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad x(t) = \frac{M_0}{m} + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{M_k}{m} \cos(2\pi f_k t + \varphi_k)$$

This means that the signal is completely defined once we know the series of transforms $X(0), X(1), \dots, X(n)$, since we can calculate from them the modules $M_k = |X(k)|$ and the phases $\varphi_k = \tan^{-1} \frac{\text{Im}[X(k)]}{\text{Re}[X(k)]}$ (the series of frequencies is assumed as known once we know the period of the signal (24)). Let us consider, as an example, the signal

$$x_q = \cos(\log t_q + 100), \quad t_q = 1107(q-1) \frac{\pi}{5}$$

for $q = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Let us consider the case $n = m - 1$ and $m = 6$. If we calculate the coefficients of Eq. 26 we find $a_0 = 0.3546$ and

$$a_1 = -0.2439, \quad a_2 = -0.2915, \quad a_3 = -0.2915, \quad a_4 = -0.2439, \quad a_5 = 0.3546,$$

$$b_1 = 3.9794 \cdot 10^{-1}, \quad b_2 = 8.9640 \cdot 10^{-2}, \quad b_3 = -8.9640 \cdot 10^{-2}, \quad b_4 = -3.9794 \cdot 10^{-1}, \quad b_5 = -3.1865 \cdot 10^{-17}$$

From these coefficients, we can derive the polynomial in Eq. 27 and plot it along with the signal (Figure 12, left). We can also calculate the DFTs of Eq. 28 and we find

$$\begin{aligned} X_0 &= 1.0639, & X_1 &= -0.7317 - 1.1938i, & X_2 &= -0.8744 - 0.2689i, \\ X_3 &= -0.8744 + 0.2689i, & X_4 &= -0.7317 + 1.1938i, & X_5 &= 1.0639 \end{aligned}$$

We can then build the signal from the transforms by the use of Eq. 29 (Figure 12 Figure 12, right). We can also calculate the modules and the phases of the components of the signal and we get

$$\begin{aligned} M_0 &= 1.0639, & M_1 &= 1.4002, & M_2 &= 0.9148, \\ M_3 &= 0.9148, & M_4 &= 1.4002, & M_5 &= 1.0639 \\ \varphi_0 &= 0, & \varphi_1 &= -2.1207, & \varphi_2 &= -2.8432, \\ \varphi_3 &= 2.8432, & \varphi_4 &= 2.1207, & \varphi_5 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

While the frequencies are $f_k = \frac{k}{T}$ for $k = 0, 1, \dots, n$. The harmonics of the signal are plotted in Figure 13. Figures and calculations for this example are generated by the script DFT.

Figure 12. The signal (black line) and the reconstructed signal obtained from Eq. 27 and Eq. 29.

All these calculations can be made automatically since each compiler offers a function for the calculation of the Fourier Transforms. In R we can use the function `fft()` which, given a discrete signal x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m , calculates the discrete transform as

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad X(k) = \sum_{q=1}^m x_q e^{-2\pi i(q-1)\frac{k-1}{m}}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

so that $X(1)$ is now what previously indicated as $X(0)$. With this notation, the reconstructed signal becomes

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad x(t) = \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{|X(k)|}{m} \cos(2\pi f_k t + \text{Arg}(X(k)))$$

with $f_k = \frac{k-1}{m}$. Note that in this document I used the same notation for the signal and for the reconstructed signal, which is probably not a good choice!

Figure 13. The signal (black line) and the harmonics (Eq. 31), each one represented in a plane defined by the respective frequency.

3.3 Periodogram

The power of the k^{th} harmonic of the signal is given by

$$\text{Eq. 34} \quad P_k = \frac{1}{m} |X(k)|^2 = \frac{1}{m} M_k^2$$

while the total power of the signal is $P_x = \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} P_k$, assuming $n = m - 1$. The plot of P_k as a function of the frequency f_k goes under the name of periodogram or power spectrum. The power between f_{k_1} and f_{k_2} is given by $\sum_{k=k_1}^{k_2} P_k$. As an example, let us consider the signal

$$\text{Eq. 35} \quad x(t) = 1.3 \sin(2\pi 15t) + 1.7 \sin(2\pi 40(t - 2)) + N(5,1)$$

where $N(5,1)$ is a normal random variable with a mean value of 5 and a standard deviation of 1. We sampled the signal every 1/100 seconds for 10 seconds (therefore $m = 1000$). The corresponding lines in R are:

```
fs<-100 # sample frequency (Hz)
t<-seq(from=0,to=(10-1/fs),by=1/fs) # time vector
m<-length(t) # number of samples
x<-1.3*sin(2*pi*15*t)+1.7*sin(2*pi*40*(t-2))+5*rnorm(m) # signal
```

Then we calculate the series of discrete Fourier transforms according to Eq. 32 and we derive the powers (Eq. 34). In R we write:

```
X<-fft(x) # discrete Fourier transform
```

```
fr<-c(0:(m-1))*fs/m # frequency range
power<-((abs(X)^2)/m) # power
```


Figure 14. Top: the signal in Eq. 35 (black) and the reconstructed signal (red) according to Eq. 33. Down: the periodogram of the signal.

We can at this point reconstruct the signal according to Eq. 33:

```
xr<-c()
for (i in 1:length(t)) {
  xr[i]<-0
  for (k in 1:m) {
    xr[i]<-xr[i]+(1/m)*abs(X[k])*cos(2*pi*t[i]*(k-1)/m+Arg(X[k]))
  }
}
```

We plot the signal, the reconstructed signal, and the periodogram (Figure 14):

```
dev.new()
par(mfrow=c(2,1))
y.lim<-c(min(x),max(x))
N<-1000
plot(t[1:N],x[1:N],type="l",lwd=1,xlim=c(t[1],t[N]),ylim=y.lim,
      xlab="time (s)",ylab="signal",col="black")
par(new=T)
plot(t[1:N],xr[1:N],type="l",lwd=3,xlim=c(t[1],t[N]),ylim=y.lim,
      xlab="",ylab="",col="red")
plot(fr,power,type="l",lwd=2,xlab="frequency (Hz)") # periodogram
```

We find the frequencies of the two components of the original signals (15 and 40 Hz) along with higher frequencies. The complete R script is on par. 4.3.

4 Scripts

4.1 DFA_proof

The following Octave code generates Figure 11.

```
% file name = DFA_proof
% date of creation = 01/02/2024
clear all
close all
m=20
k=5
#
theta=[0:0.01:pi];
figure(1)
plot(cos(theta),sin(theta),'-k', "linewidth", 2)
hold on
plot(cos(theta),-sin(theta),'-k', "linewidth", 2)
hold on
plot([-1,1],[0,0],'--k', "linewidth", 1)
hold on
plot([0,0],[-1,1],'--k', "linewidth", 1)
hold on
for i=1:m
    x=cos(2*k*pi*(i-1)/(m-1))
    y=sin(2*k*pi*(i-1)/(m-1))
    if (y>=0)
        plot([x,x],[0,y],'-b', "linewidth", 2)
    else
        plot([x,x],[0,y],'-r', "linewidth", 2)
    endif
    if (i<m)
        hold on
    endif
endfor
axis("square")
xlabel('x','fontsize',15)
ylabel('y','fontsize',15)
```

4.2 DFT

The following Octave code generates Figure 12
Figure 12 and Figure 13.

```
% file name = DFT
% date of creation = 02/02/2024
clear all
close all
%
% signal
%
m=6
n=m-1
for j=1:m
    t(j)=1107*(j-1)*pi/5;
```

```

x(j)=cos(log(t(j)+100));
endfor
T=t(m);
%
% Fourier coefficients, direct method
%
a0=(2/m)*sum(x);
for k=1:n
    a(k)=0;
    b(k)=0;
    for j=1:m
        a(k)=a(k)+(2/m)*x(j)*cos(2*k*pi*t(j)/T);
        b(k)=b(k)+(2/m)*x(j)*sin(2*k*pi*t(j)/T);
    endfor
endfor
%
t2=[0:1:T];
for j=1:length(t2)
    xDFA(j)=a0/2;
    for k=1:n
        xDFA(j)=xDFA(j)+a(k)*cos(2*k*pi*t2(j)/T)+b(k)*sin(2*k*pi*t2(j)/T);
    endfor
endfor
%
% Fourier coefficients, discrete Fourier transform
%
X0=0;
for q=1:m
    X0=X0+x(q);
endfor
for k=1:n
    X(k)=0;
    for q=1:m
        X(k)=X(k)+x(q)*exp(-1i*2*k*pi*t(q)/T);
    endfor
endfor
%
for q=1:length(t2)
    xDFT(q)=0;
    for k=1:n
        xDFT(q)=xDFT(q)+(1/m)*X(k)*exp(1i*2*k*pi*t2(q)/T);
    endfor
    for k=1:n
        xDFT(q)=xDFT(q)+(1/m)*conj(X(k))*exp(-1i*2*k*pi*t2(q)/T);
    endfor
    xDFT(q)=xDFT(q)+(1/m)*X0;
endfor
%
% modules and phases
%
M0=abs(X0);
phi0=arg(X0);
for k=1:n
    M(k)=abs(X(k));
    phi(k)=arg(X(k));
endfor
%

```

```

% 2D plotting
%
figure(1)
subplot(1,2,1)
plot(t,x,'-k', "linewidth", 2)
hold on
plot(t2,xDFA,'-r', "linewidth", 2)
xlabel("t", 'fontsize',15)
ylabel("x(t)", 'fontsize',15)
title("discrete Fourier analysis", 'fontsize',15)
legend("original signal", "Fourier interpolation", 'fontsize',15, "location", "Northeast")
%
subplot(1,2,2)
plot(t,x,'-k', "linewidth", 2)
hold on
plot(t2,xDFT,'-b', "linewidth", 2)
xlabel("t", 'fontsize',15)
ylabel("x(t)", 'fontsize',15)
title("discrete Fourier transform", 'fontsize',15)
legend("original signal", "Fourier interpolation (DFT)", 'fontsize',15, "location", "Northeast")
%
% 3D plotting
%
for k=1:n
    f(k)=k/T;
endfor
%
figure(2)
plot3(repmat(-f(1),1,m),t,x,'-k',"linewidth",2)
hold on
harmonic=repmat(M0,1,length(t2));
harmonic=harmonic/m;
plot3(repmat(0,1,length(t2)),t2,harmonic,'-r',"linewidth",2)
hold on
for k=1:n
    harmonic=M0+M(k)*cos(2*pi*f(k)*t2+phi(k));
    harmonic=harmonic/m;
    plot3(repmat(f(k),1,length(t2)),t2,harmonic,'-r',"linewidth",2)
    if (k<n)
        hold on
    endif
endfor
xlabel("frequency (Hz)", 'fontsize',15)
ylabel("time (s)", 'fontsize',15)
zlabel("signal", 'fontsize',15)

```

4.3 Periodogram

The following R script generates Figure 14.

```

dev.new()
par(mfrow=c(2,1))
y.lim<-c(min(x),max(x))
N<-1000
plot(t[1:N],x[1:N],type="l",lwd=1,xlim=c(t[1],t[N]),ylim=y.lim,
     xlab="time (s)",ylab="signal",col="black")

```

```

par(new=T)
plot(t[1:N],xr[1:N],type="l",lwd=3,xlim=c(t[1],t[N]),ylim=y.lim,
     xlab="",ylab="",col="red")
plot(fr,power,type="l",lwd=2,xlab="frequency (Hz)") # periodogram

```

4.4 NIH

The following R script performs the statistical analysis on the NIH data described in par. 1.5

```

# file name: NIH
#
# Rome, 12th February 2024
#
# read demographics
#
current_dir<-getwd()
file_name<-"datafile-demographics-dataset.csv"
file_name<-file.path(current_dir,file_name)
demo<-read.csv(file_name,sep=";",header=T)
N<-length(demo[,1])
for (i in 1:N) {
  if (demo$Group[i]==0) demo$Group[i]<-"hc"
  if (demo$Group[i]==1) demo$Group[i]<-"cfs"
}
#
# read time domain data
#
file_name<-"datafile-heart-rate-variability-data.csv"
file_name<-file.path(current_dir,file_name)
HRV<-read.csv(file_name,sep=";",header=T)
#
# add time domain data to demographic data
#
mydata<-merge.data.frame(demo,HRV,by.y="ParticipantID")
#
# read frequency domain data (only the second 5-min recording)
#
file_name<-"datafile-lf-power-data_v2.csv"
file_name<-file.path(current_dir,file_name)
LF<-read.csv(file_name,sep=";",header=T)
LF<-LF[,c(1,3)]
colnames(LF)<-c("ParticipantID","LF")
#
file_name<-"datafile-hf-power-data_v2.csv"
file_name<-file.path(current_dir,file_name)
HF<-read.csv(file_name,sep=";",header=T)
HF<-HF[,c(1,3)]
colnames(HF)<-c("ParticipantID","HF")
#
# add frequency domain data to demographic data
#
mydata<-merge.data.frame(mydata,LF,by.y="ParticipantID")
mydata<-merge.data.frame(mydata,HF,by.y="ParticipantID")
mydata$TotPower<-mydata$LF+mydata$HF # Total Power
mydata$LFnu<-mydata$LF/mydata$TotPower # normalized LF
mydata$HFnu<-mydata$HF/mydata$TotPower # normalized HF

```

```

mydata$LF_HF<-mydata$LF/mydata$HF # LF/HF
#
# statistics tests
#
mydata.CFS<-subset.data.frame(mydata,Group=="cfs")
mydata.HC<-subset.data.frame(mydata,Group=="hc")
#
test.sex<-fisher.test(rbind(table(mydata.CFS$Birth.Sex),table(mydata.HC$Birth.Sex)))
test.Age<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$Age.at.Evaluation,mydata.HC$Age.at.Evaluation,
                      alternative="two.sided")
test.BMI<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$BMI,mydata.HC$BMI,alternative="two.sided")
#
test.avgRR<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$avgRR,mydata.HC$avgRR,alternative="two.sided")
test.avgHR<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$avgHR,mydata.HC$avgHR,alternative="two.sided")
test.sdNN<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$sdNN,mydata.HC$sdNN,alternative="two.sided")
test.pNN50<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$pNN50,mydata.HC$pNN50,alternative="two.sided")
test.rMSSD<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$rMSSD,mydata.HC$rMSSD,alternative="two.sided")
#
test.LF<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$LF,mydata.HC$LF,alternative="two.sided")
test.LFnu<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$LFnu,mydata.HC$LFnu,alternative="two.sided")
test.HF<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$HF,mydata.HC$HF,alternative="two.sided")
test.HFnu<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$HFnu,mydata.HC$HFnu,alternative="two.sided")
test.TotPower<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$TotPower,mydata.HC$TotPower,alternative="two.sided")
test.LF_HF<-wilcox.test(mydata.CFS$LF_HF,mydata.HC$LF_HF,alternative="two.sided")
#
# demographics table
#
demographics<-matrix(nrow=3,ncol=3)
rownames(demographics)<-c("females/males","age","BMI")
colnames(demographics)<-c("CFS","HC","p value")
#
demographics[1,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(table(mydata.CFS$Birth.Sex)[2],"/",
table(mydata.CFS$Birth.Sex)[1]))
demographics[1,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(table(mydata.HC$Birth.Sex)[2],"/",
table(mydata.HC$Birth.Sex)[1]))
demographics[1,3]<-round(test.sex$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$Age.at.Evaluation),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$Age.at.Evaluation),digits=3)
demographics[2,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$Age.at.Evaluation),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$Age.at.Evaluation),digits=3)
demographics[2,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
demographics[2,3]<-round(test.Age$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$BMI),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$BMI),digits=3)
demographics[3,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$BMI),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$BMI),digits=3)
demographics[3,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
demographics[3,3]<-round(test.BMI$p.value,digits=3)
#
file.name<-"NIH_demographics.csv"
write.csv(demographics,file=file.name,row.names=T)
#
# results table

```

```

#
results<-matrix(nrow=11,ncol=4)
rownames(results)<-c("HR","RR","SDNN","rMSSD","pNN50","LF","LFnu","HF","HFnu","LF/HF",
"Total Power")
colnames(results)<-c("CFS","HC","p value","correction")
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$avgHR),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$avgHR),digits=3)
results[1,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$avgHR),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$avgHR),digits=3)
results[1,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[1,3]<-round(test.avgHR$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$avgRR),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$avgRR),digits=3)
results[2,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$avgRR),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$avgRR),digits=3)
results[2,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[2,3]<-round(test.avgRR$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$sdNN),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$sdNN),digits=3)
results[3,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$sdNN),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$sdNN),digits=3)
results[3,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[3,3]<-round(test.sdNN$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$rMSSD),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$rMSSD),digits=3)
results[4,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$rMSSD),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$rMSSD),digits=3)
results[4,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[4,3]<-round(test.rMSSD$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$pNN50),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$pNN50),digits=3)
results[5,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$pNN50),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$pNN50),digits=3)
results[5,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[5,3]<-round(test.pNN50$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$LF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$LF),digits=3)
results[6,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$LF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$LF),digits=3)
results[6,2]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))
results[6,3]<-round(test.LF$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$LFnu),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$LFnu),digits=3)
results[7,1]<-gsub(" ","",paste(mean,"(",sd,")"))

```

```

mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$LFnu),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$LFnu),digits=3)
results[7,2]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
results[7,3]<-round(test.LFnu$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$HF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$HF),digits=3)
results[8,1]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$HF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$HF),digits=3)
results[8,2]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
results[8,3]<-round(test.HF$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$HFnu),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$HFnu),digits=3)
results[9,1]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$HFnu),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$HFnu),digits=3)
results[9,2]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
results[9,3]<-round(test.HFnu$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$LF_HF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$LF_HF),digits=3)
results[10,1]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$LF_HF),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$LF_HF),digits=3)
results[10,2]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
results[10,3]<-round(test.LF_HF$p.value,digits=3)
#
mean<-round(mean(mydata.CFS$TotPower),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.CFS$TotPower),digits=3)
results[11,1]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
mean<-round(mean(mydata.HC$TotPower),digits=3)
sd<-round(sd(mydata.HC$TotPower),digits=3)
results[11,2]<-gsub(" ", "", paste(mean, "(", "sd, ")")
results[11,3]<-round(test.TotPower$p.value,digits=3)
#
# Benjamini-Hochberg correction
#
results[,4]<-p.adjust(results[,3],method="hochberg")
#
file.name<-"NIH_results.csv"
write.csv(results,file=file.name,row.names=T)
#
# plotting
#
jpeg("time_domain.jpeg",quality=100,res=100,width=1000,height=750)
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,2,3,4),2,2)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$avgRR,xlab="",ylab="avgRR (ms)",
      main=paste("p=",round(test.avgRR$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$avgRR,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$avgRR),mean(mydata.HC$avgRR)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$sdNN,xlab="",ylab="sdNN (ms)",

```

```

    main=paste("p=",round(test.sdNN$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$sdNN,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$sdNN),mean(mydata.HC$sdNN)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$pNN50,xlab="",ylab="pNN50",
      main=paste("p=",round(test.pNN50$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$pNN50,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$pNN50),mean(mydata.HC$pNN50)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$rMSSD,xlab="",ylab="rMSSD (ms)",
      main=paste("p=",round(test.rMSSD$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$rMSSD,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$rMSSD),mean(mydata.HC$rMSSD)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
dev.off()
#
jpeg("frequency_domain.jpeg",quality=100,res=100,width=1000,height=750)
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,3,2,4,5,6),2,3)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LF,xlab="",ylab=expression(paste("LF (",ms^{2},")")),
      main=paste("p=",round(test.LF$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LF,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$LF),mean(mydata.HC$LF)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$HF,xlab="",ylab=expression(paste("HF (",ms^{2},")")),
      main=paste("p=",round(test.HF$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$HF,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$HF),mean(mydata.HC$HF)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LFnu,xlab="",ylab="LFnu",main=paste("p=",
      round(test.LFnu$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LFnu,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$LFnu),mean(mydata.HC$LFnu)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$HFnu,xlab="",ylab="HFnu",main=paste("p=",
      round(test.HFnu$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$HFnu,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$HFnu),mean(mydata.HC$HFnu)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LF_HF,xlab="",ylab="LF/HF",main=paste("p=",
      round(test.LF_HF$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$LF_HF,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$LF_HF),mean(mydata.HC$LF_HF)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
plot(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$TotPower,xlab="",ylab=expression(paste("Total Power (",ms^{2},")")),
      main=paste("p=",round(test.TotPower$p.value,digits=3)))
points(factor(mydata$Group),mydata$TotPower,pch=21,bg="red")
points(1:2,c(mean(mydata.CFS$TotPower),mean(mydata.HC$TotPower)),pch=17,cex=1.5)
#
dev.off()

```

4.5 HRV

The following R script performs all the analysis on the 500 daily recordings (see par. 2).

```

# file name: HRV
#
# Rome, 30th January 2024
#
library(RHRV)
#
# acquire the names of the available HRV recordings
#
current_dir<-getwd()
sub_dir<-"paolo_maccallini"
folder_path<-file.path(current_dir,sub_dir)
file_names<-list.files(folder_path)
#
# store each recording in its RHRV list
#
days<-length(file_names)
hrv.data<-list()
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateHRVData()
  hrv.data[[i]]<-SetVerbose(hrv.data[[i]],T)
  date.str<-gsub(".txt","",file_names[[i]]) # remove ".txt" from file name
  date.str<-strptime(date.str,format="%Y-%m-%d %H-%M-%S")
  date.str<-format(date.str,format="%d/%m/%Y %H:%M:%S")
  hrv.data[[i]]<-LoadBeat("RR",hrv.data[[i]],file_names[[i]],
    RecordPath=folder_path,scale=0.001,datetime=date.str)
}
#
# filter the RR intervals and calculate the instantaneous non-interpolated HR
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-BuildNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])
  hrv.data[[i]]<-FilterNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])
}
#
# interpolated HR
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-InterpolateNIHR(hrv.data[[i]])
}
#
# plotting
#
PlotNIHR(hrv.data[[1]]) # non-interpolated instantaneous heart rate
PlotHR(hrv.data[[1]]) # interpolated instantaneous heart rate
RR.vec<-hrv.data[[1]]$Beat$RR
delta.bin=7.8125
vector<-seq(from=(min(RR.vec)-2*delta.bin),to=(max(RR.vec)+2*delta.bin),by=delta.bin)
hist(RR.vec,vector,xlab="RR (ms)",ylab="RR count",main="")
#
# time domain analysis
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateTimeAnalysis(hrv.data[[i]])
}
#
# plotting histograms
#

```

```

SDNN.vec<-c()
HRVi.vec<-c()
rMSSD.vec<-c()
for (i in 1:days) {
  SDNN.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$SDNN
  HRVi.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$HRVi
  rMSSD.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$TimeAnalysis[[1]]$rMSSD
}
dev.new()
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,3,2,3),2,2)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
vector<-seq(from=(min(SDNN.vec)-2*delta.bin),to=(max(SDNN.vec)+2*delta.bin),by=delta.bin)
hist(SDNN.vec,vector,xlab="SDNN (ms)",ylab="SDNN count",main="")
abline(v=mean(SDNN.vec),col="red",lwd=2)
#
vector<-seq(from=(min(HRVi.vec)-2*2),to=(max(HRVi.vec)+2*2),by=2)
hist(HRVi.vec,vector,xlab="HRVi",ylab="HRVi count",main="")
abline(v=mean(HRVi.vec),col="red",lwd=2)
#
vector<-seq(from=(min(rMSSD.vec)-2*delta.bin),to=(max(rMSSD.vec)+2*delta.bin),by=delta.bin)
hist(rMSSD.vec,vector,xlab="rMSSD (ms)",ylab="rMSSD count",main="")
abline(v=mean(rMSSD.vec),col="red",lwd=2)
#
# frequency domain analysis
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CreateFreqAnalysis(hrv.data[[i]])
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CalculatePSD(hrv.data[[i]],method="pgram",doPlot=F)
  hrv.data[[i]]<-CalculatePowerBand(hrv.data[[i]],LFmin=0.04,size=300,shift=30)
}
#
# normalized power bands
#
LFnuHFnu<-data.frame(date=c(rep(NA,days)),LFnu=c(rep(1,days)),HFnu=c(rep(1,days)))
for (i in 1:days) {
  LFnuHFnu$date[i]<-as.character(hrv.data[[i]]$datetime)
  LF<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LF
  HF<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$HF
  LFnuHFnu$LFnu[i]<-LF/(LF+HF)
  LFnuHFnu$HFnu[i]<-HF/(LF+HF)
}
#
# plotting some periodograms (logarithmic)
#
dev.new()
par(mfrow=c(2,2))
for (i in 1:4) {
  PlotPSD(hrv.data[[i]],ULFmin=NULL,ULFmax=NULL,VLFmin=NULL,VLFmax=NULL,LFmin=0.04,
    ylim=c(1e-01,1e+6),main=hrv.data[[i]]$datetime,log="y")
}
#
# plotting some periodograms (no logarithmic)
#
dev.new()
par(mfrow=c(2,2))

```

```

for (i in 1:4) {
  PlotPSD(hrv.data[[i]],ULFmin=NULL,ULFmax=NULL,VLFmin=NULL,VLFmax=NULL,LFmin=0.04,
    main=hrv.data[[i]]$datetime,log="")
}
#
# plotting histograms for power bands
#
LF.vec<-c()
HF.vec<-c()
LFHF.vec<-c()
for (i in 1:days) {
  LF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LF
  HF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$HF
  LFHF.vec[i]<-hrv.data[[i]]$FreqAnalysis[[1]]$LFHF
}
dev.new()
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,3,2,3),2,2)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
minimo<-min(LF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LF.vec,vector,xlab=expression(paste("LF (",ms^{2},")")),ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(LF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
minimo<-min(HF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(HF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(HF.vec,vector,xlab=expression(paste("HF (",ms^{2},")")),ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(HF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
minimo<-min(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LFHF.vec,vector,xlab="LF/HF",ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(LFHF.vec,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
# plotting histograms for normalized power bands
#
dev.new()
layout.mat<-matrix(c(1,2),1,2)
layout(mat=layout.mat)
layout.show(n=max(layout.mat))
#
minimo<-min(LFnuHFnu$LFnu,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LFnuHFnu$LFnu,na.rm=T)
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LFnuHFnu$LFnu,vector,xlab="LFnu",ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(LFnuHFnu$LFnu,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
#
minimo<-min(LFnuHFnu$HFnu,na.rm=T)
massimo<-max(LFnuHFnu$HFnu,na.rm=T)

```

```
delta<-(massimo-minimo)/50
vector<-seq(from=minimo-delta,to=massimo+delta,by=delta)
hist(LFnuHFnu$HFnu,vector,xlab="HFnu",ylab="count",main="")
abline(v=mean(LFnuHFnu$HFnu,na.rm=T),col="red",lwd=2)
```

5 References

The main references for this document have been the book on heart rate variability analysis with the R package RHRV (11) and the user guide of the package, *Getting Started with RHRV*, version 2.0. My main reference for the R language is the excellent book by Tilman Davies (25). All the other sources are cited within the text.

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